

higher field (low ppm scale) than chelated β -diketone. Hence, in conformity with earlier observations⁸, this confirms the presence of β -diketonate anions in the outer sphere. In addition to the above signal CH_2 and CH group proton signals of coordinated substituted pyridine, are observed at ~ 2.4 and $8-9$ ppm, respectively.

In solution, $[\text{PdL}_2](\text{ac.ac})_2$ type complexes usually dissociate to give $[\text{PdL}_2(\text{ac.ac})](\text{ac.ac})$ or $\text{Pd}(\text{ac.ac})(\text{C}^2\text{-ac.ac})^+$ type complexes. But $[\text{PdL}_2](\text{hfac})_2$ and $[\text{PdL}_2](\text{tfac})_2$ type complexes are stable in solution. Thus, in solution state, the relative stability of compounds containing β -diketonate anion in the outer sphere is in the order: $\text{ac.ac} < \text{tfac} < \text{hfac}$ ⁹, which is in accordance with the relative acid strength of the β -diketones¹⁰.

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Palladium(II) and Cobalt(III) Complexes of *p*-chloroisnitrosobenzoylacetone and *p*-bromoisnitrosobenzoylacetone

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p-CHLOROISNITROSOBENZOYLACETONE (*p*-Cl INBA) and *p*-bromoisnitrosobenzoylacetone (*p*-Br INBA) have been used as chromogenic reagents for palladium and ruthenium¹. However, structural investigations on the complexes of these ligands are lacking. In this communication we report the synthesis of solid complexes of palladium(II) and cobalt(III) with *p*-Cl INBA and *p*-Br INBA and

their characterization on the basis of magnetic susceptibility measurements, ir, uv and pmr data.

Experimental

Physical measurements: Magnetic susceptibility of the complexes was measured by Gouy method using mercury tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) as the calibrant. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Model 221 spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra were taken on a Beckman DU-2 recording spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl_3) were recorded using Varian spectrometer (100 MHz) with TMS as internal standard.

The molecular weights of the complexes were determined by cryoscopic method.

Syntheses of ligands: *p*-Cl INBA(I) and *p*-Br INBA(II) were synthesised by dropwise addition of sodium nitrite solution (4.6 g in minimum amount of water) to a solution of *p*-chloro- or *p*-bromobenzoylacetone (~ 10 g) dissolved in 30 ml of acetic acid. The reaction mixture was constantly stirred at $< 5^\circ$ and then poured into ice water when white crystals precipitate out. The crystals were collected, washed with water and recrystallised from methanol.

Syntheses of palladium and cobalt complexes of *p*-Cl INBA and *p*-Br INBA: The palladium and cobalt complexes were prepared by reacting aqueous solution of metal chlorides with ethanolic solution of *p*-Cl INBA and *p*-Br INBA in 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 molar ratios, respectively, followed by dropwise addition of either sodium acetate (for Pd, pH 4) or sodium hydroxide (for Co, pH 6) solutions till the orange-red or yellow-orange complexes precipitate out. The precipitated compounds were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum.

Results and Discussion

The palladium and cobalt complexes were found to be soluble in chloroform, benzene, ethylacetate, methanol and acetone, and insoluble in water, carbontetrachloride and petroleum ether. The analytical results (Table 1) and the molecular weights of the palladium and cobalt complexes correspond to the composition of PdL_2 and CoL_2 , respectively. Similarly, the magnetic measurements have shown them to be diamagnetic. Therefore, palladium complexes must have planer structure whereas cobalt complexes should be octahedral. Cobalt(II) thus gets oxidized to cobalt(III) during complexation with isonitroso compounds.

Pmr spectra of palladium(II) and cobalt(III) complexes in CDCl_3 exhibit phenyl proton resonance signals in the range 2.2 to 2.6 τ and methyl signals in the range 7.35 to 7.5 τ . The proton signal due to NOH observed in the ligands (Table 1) at 1.84-1.86 τ , however, disappear in the complexes suggesting that the complexation leads to the replacement of the oxime proton by the metal ion.

The selected ir bands of the ligands and the complexes are given in Table 2. The OH stretching

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA, PMR SIGNALS AND ELECTRONIC ABSORPTION BANDS OF LIGANDS AND THEIR COMPLEXES

Compd.	Decom. temp. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Pmr signals τ	$\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) kK(ϵ)
		N	Halogen	M		
<i>p</i> -Cl INBA	160*	6.25 (6.20)	15.7 (15.5)	—	1.84, 2.2-2.6, 7.5	39.5 (12790)
<i>p</i> -Br INBA	164*	5.18 (5.10)	29.6 (29.5)	—	1.86, 2.2-2.45, 7.35	38.0 (18900)
Bis(<i>p</i> -Cl INBA)Pd ^{II}	196	5.0 (5.0)	12.6 (12.7)	19.0 (19.1)	— 2.4-2.7, 7.5	39.0 (26440) 25.0 (5288)
Bis(<i>p</i> -Br INBA)Pd ^{II}	196	4.4 (4.3)	24.7 (24.7)	16.4 (16.5)	— 2.2-2.45, 7.35	38.0 (20300) 25.0 (3706)
Tris(<i>p</i> -Cl INBA)Co ^{III}	200	5.8 (5.7)	14.4 (14.5)	7.9 (8.0)	— 2.1-2.6, 7.35	40.3 (28960) 35.3 (28210) 27.7 (12460)
Tris(<i>p</i> -Br INBA)Co ^{III}	200	5.0 (4.8)	27.5 (27.7)	6.7 (6.8)	— 2.2-2.45, 7.35	39.3 (27940) 36.3 (19440) 27.7 (9959)

* Melting point.

TABLE 2—SOME IMPORTANT VIBRATIONAL BANDS AND ASSIGNMENTS IN LIGANDS AND THEIR COMPLEXES

<i>p</i> -Cl INBA	Pd ^{II} (<i>p</i> -Cl INBA)	Co ^{III} (<i>p</i> -Cl INBA)	<i>p</i> -Br INBA	Pd ^{II} (<i>p</i> -Br INBA)	Co ^{III} (<i>p</i> -Br INBA)	Assignment
3380 s	—	—	3275 s	—	—	Hydrogen bonded OH stretching of O=NOH
1675 s	1650 s	1650 s	1670 s	1645 m	1650 s	C=O stretching
1620 m	—	—	1610 m	—	—	C=N stretching
1590 s	1590 m	1590 m	1580 s	1580 w	1590 m	Perturbed C=N stretching
—	1525 m	1525 m	—	1510 w	1520 m	Bonded C=O stretching
1225 w	1225 s	1225 s	1225 w	1230 m	1230 m	NO stretching
1090 s	1080 m	1085 s	1070 s	1065 s	1065 m	CN stretching

frequency exhibited by the ligands disappears in the palladium and cobalt complexes and confirms the result of pmr studies that the complex formation involves replacement of the hydrogen atom of the NOH group by the metal atom. The strong band at 1650-1645 cm⁻¹ in metal complexes is assigned to C=O of the aromatic ketone and is indicative of the symmetric nature of the complexes. The weak band at 1620-1610 cm⁻¹ in the ligand is assigned to C=N stretching², which shifts to 1590-1580 cm⁻¹ in the metal complexes. The band at 1525-1510 cm⁻¹ in the complexes is assigned to bonded C=O stretching. The band at 1230-1225 cm⁻¹ may be tentatively attributed to N-oxide stretching frequency. This is consistent with the fact that the N-oxide peak in aromatic ring compounds occurs as a strong band in the region 1300-1200 cm⁻¹. Further it is reported that tris(dimethylglyoximinato)-cobalt(III)³ and tris(isonitrosoacetylacetonato)-cobalt(III)⁴ having 5-membered ring structures, exhibit N-oxide band at 1221 and 1292 cm⁻¹, respectively. The ir and pmr data suggest that the diamagnetic palladium and cobalt complexes of *p*-Cl INBA and *p*-Br INBA may be formulated by the following structures.

where, R is CH₃, R' is C₆H₅ group containing either Cl or Br, and M may be Pd^{II} or Co^{III}.

The electronic spectra of the ligands in chloroform exhibit an intense band at 39.5 kK (*p*-Cl INBA) and 38.0 kK (*p*-Br INBA). This band is attributed to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition in the ligand. The palladium complexes show one additional band at 25 kK which can be assigned to charge transfer transition. The charge transfer transition in cobalt(III) complexes, however, occurs at 27.7 kK. In view of the high intensity of charge transfer transitions the d-d bands are obscured and are not visible in the absorption spectrum of the complexes.

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Cobalt(II) and Zinc(II) Phenylacetate Complexes with Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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THORNTON *et al.* have reported¹ some Ni^{II} complexes of benzoates and substituted benzoates with heterocyclic amine ligands. More recently Guru *et al.* have also reported² some phenylacetate complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with nitrogen donor ligands. In the present communication we report some mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} and Zn^{II} phenylacetates with different nitrogen donor ligands.

Experimental

Ethanol solutions of Zn^{II} and Co^{II} phenylacetates were mixed with different nitrogen donor ligands in stoichiometric ratio and the resulting solutions were refluxed on water bath for 2 h. The 2,2'-dipyridine and 1,10-phenanthroline complexes separated out on shaking and cooling, while the pyridine and γ -picoline complexes were obtained after keeping the solution for more than 24 h. The complexes were filtered under suction, washed with

ethanol and ether and dried over anhydrous CaCl₂ in a vacuum desiccator.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes of zinc are white crystalline solid and those of cobalt are pink crystalline and have the composition ML₂B₂ or ML₂B', where B=pyridine and γ -picoline and B'=2,2'-dipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline. The compounds are soluble in acetone in which medium they behave as non-electrolyte, as the Δ_M values are low being 9 to 15 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ (Table 1). All the cobalt(II) compounds are paramagnetic with μ_{eff} values 4.9 to 5.1 B.M. indicating the octahedral stereochemistry. The high spin octahedral cobalt(II) complexes have³ large orbital contributions to spin only values and the magnetic moments are found to vary from 4.7 to 5.2 B.M. The high orbital contribution is attributable to the three-fold orbital degeneracy of the ⁴T_{1g} ground state.

In free sodium phenylacetate asymmetric and symmetric C=O stretching frequencies appear at 1610 and 1400 cm⁻¹, respectively⁴. In metal phenylacetates these bands appear slightly to a lower frequency region, but again shifts to higher frequency region in case of mixed ligand complexes indicating that both phenylacetate and the nitrogen donor ligands are bonded to the metal ion. Further, most of the absorption bands due to free nitrogen ligands are also modified indicating⁵ their coordination to the metal ion. The far ir spectra of the three complexes exhibit two bands at $\sim 350 \nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ and $\sim 250 \text{ cm}^{-1} \nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$. These bands further confirm that both phenylacetate and nitrogen donor ligands are bonded to the metal ion. The difference between the asymmetric and symmetric stretching $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ mode of complexes are of the order 210-220 cm⁻¹ indicating the bidentate nature of the phenylacetate as this difference will be of higher order for monodentate acetate group.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour and form	Δ_0 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)	
				M	N
CoL ₂ (Py) ₂	Pink crystalline	9.5	4.80	12.00 (12.04)	5.68 (5.72)
CoL ₂ (γ -Pic) ₂	Pink crystalline	10.0	5.10	11.32 (11.40)	5.40 (5.44)
CoL ₂ (2,2'-Dipy)	Pink crystalline	11.2	4.96	11.97 (12.04)	5.65 (5.72)
CoL ₂ (1,10-Phen)	Rosy crystalline	11.8	4.96	11.92 (11.56)	5.47 (5.49)
ZnL ₂ (Py) ₂	White crystalline	13.0	—	13.10 (13.18)	5.60 (5.65)
ZnL ₂ (γ -Pic) ₂	White crystalline	14.5	—	12.45 (12.54)	5.30 (5.37)
ZnL ₂ (2,2'-Dipy)	White crystalline	14.0	—	13.05 (13.18)	5.60 (5.65)
ZnL ₂ (1,10-Phen)	White crystalline	13.8	—	12.60 (12.67)	5.38 (5.42)

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